

GNOSEOLOGICAL DISCOURSE IN ISLAMIC THEOLOGY AND RELIGION

Ulugmuradov Elyor Saidullaevich

Teacher of

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages,
Uzbekistan, Samarkand

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10565956>

Abstract: The article reveals some components of Islamic religious epistemology and draws parallels with other religious epistemologies. Special attention is paid to the formula of religious creationism, and its epistemological, physical, symbolic and other meanings are emphasized. Different variants of creationism are listed and the specificity of their manifestation in Islam is investigated.

Keywords: epistemology, religious epistemology, Islam, creationism, being and non-being, worldviews atomistic concept, determinism and indeterminism.

Gnoseological concepts in various forms of worldviews have always existed and will always exist. After all, epistemology is a fundamental part of any picture of the world and any worldview. This expresses the inevitable human aspiration to a priori and integral constructions of the universe and to find out the place of man in them. In accordance with the historical types of worldviews we can distinguish several types of such epistemologies: mythological, religious, philosophical, which, in all their interrelation, represent independent models of comprehension of existence.

Therefore, the main epistemological categories, such as being and nothingness, matter and consciousness, real and ideal, motion, space and time, determinism and some others, began to form already in the mythological worldview. In religion, this process continued intensively, and finally the modern status of an independent sphere of knowledge gnoseology received in philosophy.

The Central Asian theologian Abu Mansur al-Maturidi (d. 332) was one of the first to formulate the basic epistemological approaches (asbab al'ilm) within the framework of cognition of doctrinal problems. Later they formed the basis of a new doctrinal school of Islam, the followers of which today are about half of Sunni Muslims.

The earliest references to Abu Mansur al-Maturidi are found in the theological treatises of Hanafi scholars - followers of the Imam¹. Among them, Abu Yusra al-Bazdawi (d. 493/1100) should be mentioned first of all, who writes about him as follows.

As is well known, the Sunni creed in the course of its historical development had to compete with a large number of currents that began to emerge as early as the first century AH (the sixth century according to the Gregorian chronology). Accordingly, this required the development of the basic principles of theological knowledge that would allow for a reasoned discussion, answering the doubts of opponents as well as their distinctive ideas. An analysis of the content of the works of Imam Abu Hanifa (699-767) and the representative of Western Hanafism, Imam at-Tahawi (843/853-935), shows that they do not pay attention to this issue. The earliest in this regard is "Kitab at-Tawhid". Later, we see the tradition of expounding the epistemological theory in the treatise "Tabsirat al-adillah" (Consideration of arguments) by Abu Mu'ina al-Nasafi (1046-1115) and the creedal text by Abu Hafsa al-Nasafi².

Al-Maturidi calls his opponents *sufasta'iyā* (sophists). About their understanding of this issue he writes: "The sophists said: "Since we have found that man knows something and then it becomes untenable, feels a sweetness which then disappears, and some of the land animals die in the sea and some of the sea animals die on land, man sees bats at night and does not see during the day - all this indicates the untenability of knowledge. This all constitutes mere belief and is different from knowledge.""". Clearly, we are talking about agnostics and skeptics here, and the term "sophists" has a narrower meaning. At first glance, it may seem that the Imam is making an error in the use of the term. In fact, using it in the way al-Maturidi does is related to the principle of *al-hukm 'ala az-zahir* "judgment based on the literal meaning of the opponent's words." Since al-Maturidi's opponents resorted to formal logical methods, he called them "sophists."

In the beginning of the text "Kitab at-tauhid" al-Maturidi himself stated: "The paths leading to the knowledge of the true essence of things are sensation (*'iyan*)³, knowledge (*khabar*) and reflection (*akl*)".

From the theologian's quotation, the first conclusion to be drawn is that in matters of cognition he took the position of epistemological optimists who

¹ Al-Bazdawi M. *Usul ad-din*. Kair: al-Maktaba al-azkhariia li at-turas; 2003. 271 s.

² Al-Maturidi M. *Tavilat akhl as-sunna*. T. 1. Basillum M. (red.). Beirut: Dar al-kutub al-'ilmiia; 2005. 646 s.

³ Al-Kurashi 'A. *al-Dzhavakhir al-mudi'a fi tabakat al-khanafiia*. T. 3. Dar al-khidzhra; 1993. 504 s.

recognized the possibility of reliable knowledge of the world. Later, his follower al-Nasafi would summarize this idea with the words: "The essences of things are established and their cognition is feasible".

From his words we can conclude that in matters of doctrine he considers three ways of knowledge permissible: the senses, tradition and reason. Regarding cognition by means of the senses, he states: "By sensation is meant that information which we receive through the senses. This is the basic path that provides knowledge, which has no such opposite as ignorance." It follows from the Imam's words that he recognized the information obtained by this way of knowledge as inherently reliable, which coincides with the foundations of the empiricist attitude of natural scientific knowledge. However, in the field of doctrine, this way of knowledge is only intermediate.

Islamic epistemology, on the one hand, corresponds to all the features of religious epistemology in general; on the other hand, it has distinctive features. Here are some of the common features of religious epistemology:

- All religious doctrines have an epistemological concept formed from worldview postulates that have primarily ethical meaning. Therefore, any epistemological construction, every event, thing, process is important not in itself, but as expressions, symbols of the interaction of the two universal forces of good and evil, which have a deep moral motive;

- religious epistemologies are the most influential compared to other, more tolerant epistemologies. Due to centuries of indoctrination, religious abstractions and symbols have become important components of surrounding reality. Religious narratives are organically embedded in the cultural, linguistic, and mental foundations of a people's existence. This is especially true for the Islamic religion with its absolute monotheism⁴, the mechanisms of which are directly woven into people's life practice, communication and everyday life;

- it is syncretic, since the epistemological maxim is the basis of any worldview construct. This means that all other forms of spiritual mastering of the world: mythology, morality, art, philosophy, science are constantly present in this epistemological scheme.

One important ontological circumstance follows from this. God cannot be positively defined at all through the enumeration of attributes and attribution; he can only be understood negatively through terms of absence: unattainable, incomprehensible, unfathomable, immaterial, unmanifest. Therefore, according to apophatic theology, He is not "likened" to anything, nor does He reveal His

⁴ Kasikov V.I. Ontologii.[The Ontologies] *Voprosy filosofii [Issues of Philosophy]* 2013, № 9. – S. 43–51.

divine essence in anything. Even the basic way of defining concepts in logic - by subsuming the concept to be defined under a more general category - is not suitable for this, since God is beyond any existential metric, and therefore there is simply no broader concept to which He can be compared.

Thus, even the logic of comprehending and defining God contradicts the rational mechanisms of human comprehension of the world. On the one hand, He cannot be comprehended exhaustively through positive attribution; on the other hand, we all know well the logical rule that a definition should not consist only of negative terms; at least one attribute must be a positive term.

References:

1. Меликова М. Н. РАЗВИТИЕ КУЛЬТУРЫ И ПРЕОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ОБЛАСТИ ТУРИЗМА В ГОРОДАХ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ // Innovative processes in economic, social and spiritual spheres of life of society. – 2018. – С. 15-17.
2. Улугмуродов, Элёр Сайдуллоевич. "ФИЛОСОФСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ ИСЛАМА В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ." ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ПОЛИТОЛОГИЯ, СОЦИОЛОГИЯ, ФИЛОСОФИЯ, ИСТОРИЯ. 2020.
3. KHOLIKOV, Y. O. (2021). THE EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE ON THE BASIS OF A SPIRITUAL, MORAL AND TOLERANT CULTURE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences, 1(2), 63-68.
4. Saydulloevich, Ulugmurodov Elyor. "ISLAMIC CULTURE: THE ESSENCE AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT." Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research 3.03 (2022): 208-212.
5. Улуғмуродов, Элёр Сайдуллоевич. "Диний қадриятлар ва тасвирий санъат интеграциясининг ёшлар эстетик тафаккурига таъсири." Oriental Art and Culture II (2020): 52-59.
6. SAYDULLOEVIC, ULUGMURODOV ELYOR. "Yoshlarning estetik tafakkurini shakllantirishda islomiy qadriyatlarining falsafiy tahlili". JournalNX 6.05: 162-169.

